

COMPOSITES OPTIMIZATION USING LAMINATION PARAMETERS IN AN ENGINEERING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Structural optimization using so-called lamination parameters for composite shells was implemented in a FEM based code for shape, size and material optimization. A general system for optimization of composite shells was thus obtained. Some preliminary results from a comparison between optimization using lamination parameters and optimization using ply thicknesses in a ($0^\circ, 90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ$) layup in a simplified aircraft rudder structure are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Structural optimization concerning both size and shape of structures made of isotropic material did during the last decade very much mature and engineering structures are now optimized on a routine basis using optimization systems such as OASIS-ALADDIN developed by Esping, Holm and coworkers [1,2]. Optimization of composite material shell structures though still lacks behind. The latter can be cast as a combinatorial task – the placement of fiber plies through the thickness yields completely different bending properties. Alternatively ply angles and thicknesses can be used as design variables, but at least angle variables tend to lead to prohibitively nonlinear optimization tasks with numerous local optima. Lamination parameters, introduced by Tsai and Pagano [3] for plates with Kirchhoff kinematics and extended to Reissner-Mindlin kinematics by Grenestedt [4], simplify analysis and some problems even become convex [5,6]. Further, all physically possible layups of one material can simply be included with only twelve lamination parameters. The present paper is a summary of an implementation of composite shell optimization using lamination parameters in the OASIS-ALADDIN general optimization code.

THE OASIS-ALADDIN STRUCTURAL OPTIMIZATION SYSTEM

The lamination parameter optimization was implemented in a system consisting of the OASIS software for structural optimization and the ALADDIN pre/post processor. OASIS-ALADDIN is a general optimization system which handles different kinds of design variables including shape, thickness, material orientation, and material properties. Stresses, displacements, eigenfrequencies, weight, and mass moment of inertia can be used as objective and constraint functions. The optimization problem is solved iteratively where in each iteration a convex and separable subproblem is created and solved. The subproblem is created from information of function and gradient values of the main problem. The sequence of subproblems usually converges to a (local) optimum of the main problem within ten iterations. The convergence speed in terms of number of iterations is roughly independent of the number of design variables and constraints, but depends strongly on the nonlinearity of the objective and constraint functions. The computational cost of each iteration is approximately linear in the number of design variables and constraints.

SHORT ABOUT LAMINATION PARAMETERS AND FAILURE CRITERIA

Lamination parameters are 12 parameters which uniquely describe the plate stiffnesses of layered composite material Kirchhoff and Reissner-Mindlin plates. The plate stiffnesses are linear in the lamination parameters, a fact which leads to convexity for certain optimization problems [5,6]. There is no unique layout corresponding to a set of lamination parameters. Ordinarily used failure criteria, such as Azzi-Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, etc., can therefore not be used since these require information about the stress state relative to material orthotropy axes. In order to include material strength in the optimization with lamination parameters, a failure criterion which depends only on the invariants of in-plane strains was constructed. A simple but presumably fairly accurate failure criterion is to use bounds on in-plane tensile and compressive strains, and disregard through-the-thickness strains. In other words,

$$-\varepsilon_c \leq \varepsilon_2 \leq \varepsilon_1 \leq \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where ε_1 and ε_2 are the largest and smallest in-plane strains, respectively, ε_t is the maximum allowed in-plane tensile strain, and ε_c is the maximum allowed absolute value of in-plane compressive strain. ε_1 and ε_2 are principal strains when the shear strains ε_{13} and ε_{23} are negligible, which presently was assumed (the x_3 direction is perpendicular to the shell middle surface). The failure criterion is depicted for Mohr circles in Fig. 1. It may be beneficial to include a shear strain cut-off,

$$\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2 \leq 2\varepsilon_s \quad (2)$$

where ε_s is the maximum allowed (absolute value of) in-plane shear strain. This failure criterion is also depicted in Fig. 1, but was not implemented in the FE code.

A clear advantage with the failure criteria of eqs. (1) and (2) is that with a linear strain distribution through the thickness, as in shells with Love-Kirchhoff or Reissner-Mindlin kinematics, the most critical points will always be at the shell surfaces. This is in contrast with

more common failure criteria which for each ply have to be evaluated at least in two locations through the thickness.

Fig. 1. Two isotropic strain failure envelopes for Mohr circles. To the left is the failure envelope when there are limits on tensile and compressive strains, to the right is the failure envelope when there are limits on shear strain γ too.

IMPLEMENTATION OF LAMINATION PARAMETERS IN THE OPTIMIZATION SYSTEM

The OASIS structural optimization system uses the BASIS finite element (FE) code, in which a version of the Ahmad [7] shear deformable shell element is implemented. The stiffnesses of the Ahmad type shell element are expressed with lamination parameters in the same way as the stiffnesses of Reissner-Mindlin shear deformable plates are expressed in [4]. As failure criterion, eq. (1) is suitable. The implementation of lamination parameters in the FE code is now, at least in theory, straight forward.

For the implementation in the optimization code the range of the lamination parameters is needed. The complete range has still not been determined analytically apart from under special circumstances. A number of approximations have been obtained, some of which are summarized in [6]; most of these were included in the present implementation. Further, since it is known that the range is convex and tangent planes to the boundary of the range can be determined with the approach of [6], a faceted outer boundary of the range can be constructed and used for the optimization. This can be done by once calculating a large number of such facets and storing them in a data base, and later use it during the optimization. This has been implemented but was presently not used.

A problem with the optimization was that every once in a while lamination parameters outside their range were delivered from the optimizer to the FE code for analysis. If the corresponding stiffness matrix was not positive definite, the FE analysis would crash. Therefore a subroutine, called after the optimizer has determined new lamination parameters but before the FE code has received them, checked if the corresponding stiffness matrix was positive definite and – if not – reduced the lamination parameters slightly until positive definiteness was obtained. The reduction was done by multiplying all lamination parameters with a constant slightly smaller than 1 repeatedly until positive definiteness was guaranteed. When

all lamination parameters are zero the laminate becomes isotropic with a positive definite stiffness matrix, assuming the input layer moduli are appropriate.

After the optimization had finished, one problem still remained – how to obtain a discrete layup from the optimal lamination parameters. This is the second task which currently is unsolved. Our approach to the problem was very pragmatic – by a kind of trial-and-error method combined with optimization a large number of discrete laminates were investigated. Usually rather good approximations to the lamination parameters could be obtained in this way. The approach is naturally not completely satisfactory.

APPLICATION TO A SIMPLIFIED AIRCRAFT RUDDER STRUCTURE

After elementary examples such as flat plates subject to uniform pressure and round cylinders subject to torsion had been successfully optimized, a more extensive task including thickness and layup optimization of a representative structure of engineering interest was initiated. Shape optimization was also prepared but is not reported here. The structure selected was a simplified aircraft rudder structure (aileron, spoiler,...) according to Fig. 2. The rudder consisted of an aluminum C-spar which was attached to a hinge in each corner of the top flange of the spar and an actuator in between attached to the lower flange, a top and a bottom composite material skin and a light sandwich core between the skins. The structure was symmetric and thus only half the structure was modeled. The skins were slightly curved in such a way that the top skin was convex and the bottom skin concave. The skin thickness was not uniform but there were three regions in each skin with different thicknesses. Close to the hinge and actuator attachments the skin thicknesses would increase. The thicknesses were determined by thickness optimization and the layup either by using lamination parameter or by using ply thicknesses in a layup with a certain number of plies with fixed orientations.

Fig. 2. FE model of half of the simplified rudder structure. At (a) symmetry boundary conditions were applied. The hinge was located at (b). The regions with different layups and thicknesses are marked with no shading, light, and dark shading, respectively.

The loading was a normal pressure (0.05 MPa) on the concave side of the rudder. Material parameters were approximately those of carbon fiber T300-5208 composite and Rohacell 31 foam and are given in Table 1. The out-of-plane moduli of the composite are not reliable but this was expected to be of little consequence due to the thin skins.

The C-spar and each of the two composite skins were modeled as thin shear deformable shells and the core as a 3D solid. Stresses in the C-spar were disregarded and neither shape nor thicknesses of the spar were included in the optimization. Von Mises' yield function was used as failure criterion for the core material.

Table 1. Material parameters used for the optimization of the rudder structure.

	stiffness	strength (incl. safety factor 1.5)	density
carbon composite (approx. T300-5208)	$E_1=181$ GPa $E_2=10.3$ GPa $G_{12}=7.17$ GPa $\nu_{12}=0.28$	$\epsilon_t=0.8$ % $\epsilon_c=0.5$ % $s_1^t = 1448$ MPa $s_1^c = 905$ MPa	$\rho=1600$ kg/m ³
sandwich core (approx. Rohacell 31)	$E=21.2$ MPa $\nu=0.14$	$\sigma_{cr}=0.15$ MPa	$\rho=32$ kg/m ³

Three optimization cases were performed in a first test series. These were:

- (A) optimization using 12 lamination parameters plus skin thickness,
- (B) optimization using 15 ply thicknesses in a discrete
(0°,90°,+45°,-45°,0°,90°,+45°,-45°,+45°,90°,0°,-45°,+45°,90°,0°) layup as design variables, and
- (C) optimization using 7 ply thicknesses in a discrete
(0°,90°,+45°,-45°,+45°,90°,0°) layup as design variables.

The same FE model, illustrated in Fig. 2, with 6 regions with different thicknesses and layups was used for the three cases. The number of design variables was thus (A) 6*13=78 (12 lamination parameters and one thickness in each of the six regions), (B) 6*15=90, and (C) 6*7=42.

The strain based failure criterion, eq. (1), could not be used for cases (B) and (C) but rather a fiber stress criterion was used,

$$-s_1^c \leq \sigma_1 \leq s_1^t \quad (3)$$

where σ_1 is stress in the fiber direction of a ply. This criterion can be interpreted as a simple version of the Tsai-Hill criterion. The parameters were set to

$$\begin{aligned} s_1^t &= E_1 \epsilon_t \\ s_1^c &= E_1 \epsilon_c \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and are also given in Table 1. This criterion and the first-ply-failure assumption result in a failure envelope which for a (0°,90°,±45°) laminate is close to that of the strain failure criterion which was used for the optimization with lamination parameters.

The objective function for the optimization was the weight of the rudder. Constraints were put on laminate and core stresses in accordance with Table 1, and deflection of the corners of the rudder. The corners outside the hinges were required not to deflect more than 20 mm relative to the attachments on the C-spar. There was a thickness constraint in each region of the composite skins. The results from the three optimizations are summarized in Table 2. Since geometry, loading, sizes, deformation constraints, etc. are not realistic, only the relative performance of the three cases should be considered. The weight was therefore normalized against the weight obtained from the optimization using lamination parameters.

Table 2. Summary of the first optimization results of a simplified rudder structure.

case	A	B	C
type of design variables	lam. parameters & total thickness	ply thicknesses in a (0,90 ±45) layup	ply thicknesses in a (0,90 ±45) layup
# design variables	78	90	42
optimal weight (relative)	1.00	1.00	1.10
# iterations	4	7	6
active constraint	deformation	deformation	deformation

For this particular case, a discrete (0,90,±45) layup with 15 ply thicknesses in each region as design variables apparently was sufficient to obtain what is believed to be a global optimum, with the same weight as obtained from the optimization using lamination parameters. The reason is likely to be that this structure is such that the structural response mainly depends on the in-plane properties of the composite skins. Larger weight savings from using lamination parameters are expected when more of the stiffnesses (in-plane, bending, coupling) play an important role for the structural response.

DISCUSSION

There are a few obvious problems related to optimization using lamination parameters. The fact that a general failure criterion cannot be used is believed to be only a minor one. More crucial is to obtain a better approximation to the range of the lamination parameters, and to develop refined post-processing for determination of a discrete layup from optimal values of the lamination parameters.

For the simple rudder structure above, optimization using a discrete layup with 15 design variables in each region performed as well as optimization using 12 lamination parameters and a thickness in each region. Larger differences, to the advantage of lamination parameter optimization, is expected for structures whose structural response depends more on all stiffnesses (in-plane, bending, coupling). This will naturally be evaluated in the future.

This report is a first summary of an implementation of lamination parameter optimization in an engineering structural optimization system. Numerous problems still have to be resolved but in general the approach appears to have a fair chance to substantially improve optimization of composite material shell structures.

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